

FUNDAMENTALS OF ALGORITHMIZATION AND PROGRAMMING

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Abstract: *Basic concepts of Algorithms, Types of Algorithms, Fundamentals of Programming.*

Key words: *Algorithmization, Programming C++.*

The word "algorithm" is derived from the word "algorithm", it is the Latin form of the name of the great mathematician of the 9th century, Muhammad al-Khorazmi. In the field of informatics, the concept of algorithm is a basic concept, and it is a fundamental concept like a point, a straight line and a plane in a geometry course, a set in mathematics, a substance in chemistry, and the concepts of space and time in physics. It is difficult to give a precise definition to the algorithm. Nevertheless, the essence of the algorithm can be clearly explained. An algorithm is an ordered sequence of commands that must be executed to solve a problem. The created algorithm can be executed by a person who understands the rules of its writing and is able to execute the commands specified in it, or by a technical device (for example, a computer)

People unknowingly use algorithms to perform their daily tasks. For example, using a computer, baking bread, cooking, using a telephone machine, driving a car, reading a book, obeying the rules of street traffic, using television or radio, etc. Of course, since people always perform the above tasks, they do not feel the need for any specific instructions to perform them. But the person performing the above tasks for the first time cannot do it without clear instructions. For example, a person who has never used a computer cannot do this without specific instructions. So, people sometimes received or learned the instructions necessary to perform familiar tasks or issues. When performing the algorithm, it is necessary to follow the instructions in the given order.

Algorithm and its properties

Before the advent of electronic calculators, different DEFINITIONS were given to the algorithm. But all of them are very close to each other in terms of meaning, and this definition is currently interpreted as follows.

DESCRIPTION. Algorithm refers to a finite sequence of actions performed according to a known rule to solve a given problem.

Any algorithm is executed according to certain instructions, and these instructions are called instructions.

The algorithm has the following important properties:

Clarity and comprehensibility means that the instructions given to the executor in the algorithm are clear.

Popularity means that according to the content of each algorithm, it is suitable for all problems of the same type.

Efficiency means that the algorithm will definitely produce a result after a finite number of steps.

Discretization means the ability to divide algorithms into finite steps.

Algorithm types

There are three types of algorithms: linear, branching and iterative.

A linear algorithm is unconditionally referred to only sequentially executed processes.

A branching algorithm is an algorithm composed of instructions that are executed according to certain conditions.

An iterative algorithm is a process in which repetition occurs in the algorithm based on the verification of a condition or different values of a parameter.

Algorithms can be described in different ways. For example: verbalization; giving in formulas; representation in block diagrams; expression in the form of a program, etc.

Algorithms are often used because they are easy and understandable to describe in block diagram form. In this case, each instruction in the algorithm has its own form. For example: parallelogram symbol in view of input and output of data; the process of calculating the rectangular sign; a diamond symbol indicates that conditions are checked.

In our life, we use algorithms in various fields knowingly and unknowingly. Algorithms are not only mathematical in nature, but we use them a lot in our everyday life. For example, preparing food, making tea, doing a task, etc. In doing these things, we will follow the specific instructions that are known. If these instructions are not followed in a specific sequence, we will not get the desired result. As an example, let's consider the non-mathematical bottle bread preparation algorithm. The starters are: bread, sausage and cheese. Result: bottle bread. Algorithm for making bread:

1. Cutting a piece of bread;
2. Cut a slice of sausage and cheese;

3. Put the sausage and cheese layer between the bread Bo Bo layer.

If the sequence of this process is reversed or any step is not performed, the result will be No.

Algorithmic languages

After the algorithm for solving the problem is developed, the program is compiled. A program is a set of instructions, that is, commands or operators, written in an algorithmic language based on a given algorithm. Programming is the process of creating a program, which consists of the following steps:

1. Requirements for the program;
2. choosing or developing an algorithm for the given problem;
3. write program codes (texts, commands);
4. correcting and testing the program.

Nowadays, there are many algorithmic languages. We call them programming languages. An algorithmic language is a system of notations and rules used to write algorithms uniformly and precisely. Algorithmic language is close to ordinary language in that it contains mathematical symbols. The constructed algorithm cannot be given directly to the machine, therefore it is necessary to translate the written algorithm into some algorithmic language. Any algorithmic language has its own field of application. For example, Pascal, BASIC and Fortran in engineering calculations. Pascal and Cobol in solving economic problems. Prolog and others for logic programming. Basic, Pascal, etc. for learning processes.

Pascal, Fortran, and Cobol are universal languages. Assembly language is a language very close to machine language and is an intermediate level language. The closer an algorithmic language is to human languages, the more it is called a high-level language. And machine language is the lowest level language.

Troubleshooting steps

The steps to solve the problem on the computer are as follows:

1. Set the problem and develop its mathematical model. At this stage, the initial data content is defined. Problem formulation is usually completed by verbally describing the main features of the problem to be solved and then writing a mathematical model of the problem.

2. Choosing a solution method. After the problem is expressed mathematically, the method of solving it is chosen. It determines whether the desired results depend on the initial data. Modern

computational mathematics has a large number of methods for solving various problems related to science and technology.

3. Development of a problem solving algorithm. At this stage, the sequence of actions (commands) performed on the computer to solve the problem is described. We call it algorithmization.

4. Programming. In this case, the algorithm is decomposed into an algorithmic language.

5. Entering the program and correcting errors.

6. Solve the problem directly on the computer and analyze the results. In this case, the necessary initial values are given in the program, the result is obtained and analyzed on the computer. At this stage, if necessary, the algorithm and the program can be modernized. Necessary conclusions are developed on the basis of newly obtained information. This information serves to analyze the issue in different ways, to understand complex processes, to discover global news, to create new theories and technical miracles. In general, the trinity "Model-algorithm-program" constitutes the intellectual core of modeling, without such a trinity, it is impossible to achieve success in solving complex problems on a computer.

Fundamentals of programming

The user is also required to know computer "language" to communicate with the computer. A "language" that a computer understands is called a programming language. To solve a problem on a computer, first of all, it is necessary to create its algorithm and write this algorithm based on the instructions and rules that the computer understands. This record consists of a consistent sequence of instructions that the program can execute. The process of creating a program for a computer is programming and the person who creates the program is called a programmer.

Today, there are high-level programming languages for computing, engineering, economics, textual and numerical data analysis, and solving other problems. These include Basic, Fortran, Pascal, Cobol and other languages.

The BASIC programming language was created in 1964 by John Kemeny and Thomas Curtsey, researchers at the University of Dortmund in the United States, to solve various computational problems through communication with a computer. The word "Basic" is derived from Beginners Allpurpose Symbolic Instruction Code, and in Uzbek it means "multipurpose symbolic instruction language intended for beginners".

Because of BASIC's simplicity and low memory requirements, BASIC has become the most widely used programming language for personal computers around the world, along with other programming languages.

The Fortran language was developed in 1954. The word "Fortran" is derived from the English word "Formula translator" and means formula translator. Fortran language is a programming language intended for solving engineering and scientific and technical problems.

Pascal programming language was created by Swiss professor Wirt Nicklaus in 1971, and in 1981 the international standard of Pascal language was adopted. The Pascal language is named after the French physicist Blaise Pascal, who created the adding machine. Pascal language is widely used in solving scientific, technical and engineering problems.

The Kobol language was created in 1959 and is intended to solve economic problems.

Currently, the Delphi programming language, which is considered one of the modern programming languages, is widely used. Delphi is a programming language designed to run on the Windows OS environment and was created in 1995 by Chuck and Danny, a group of programmers at Borland. This program differs from other programming languages by some of its features. For this reason, today Delphi programming language is included in science programs of academic lyceums, vocational colleges and universities.

The C++ programming language is based on the C language. C, in turn, is derived from B and BCPL. BCPL was created by Martin Richards in 1967 and was intended for writing operating systems. Ken Thompson introduced many features of BCPL in his B language and wrote the first versions of the UNIX operating system in B. Both BCPL and B were typeless languages. That is, there was no specific type of variable - each variable occupied only one byte of computer memory. It was up to the programmer to use the variable as an integer, a fractional number, or a letter.

Dennis Ritchie derived C from B and first used it in 1972 at Bell Labs on the DEC PDP-11 computer. C includes many important aspects of its predecessors B and BCPL, as well as variable typing and a number of other innovations. In the beginning, C was mainly used on UNIX systems. Currently, most operating systems are written in C/C++. C is a language bound to machine architecture. But with good planning, programs can be made to work on different computer platforms.

In 1983, as the C language became more popular, efforts to standardize it began. For this, the X3J11 technical committee was formed under the American National Standards Committee (ANSI). This standard was adopted in 1989. In 1990, ANSI and the International Organization for Standardization (ISO) jointly adopted ANSI/ISO 9899:1990 for C in order to spread the standard around the world. Because of this, programs written in C will run on most computer platforms with little or no changes.

C++ was developed in the early 1980s by Bjarne Stroustrup, based on C. C++ has many extensions, but most importantly it allows programming with objects.

Fast and high-quality writing of programs is of great importance nowadays. To ensure this, the idea of object-oriented programming was put forward. Like structured programming in the early 1970s, building programs through objects that model real-life objects revolutionized the field of programming.

In addition to C++, other multi-objective programming languages have emerged. The most prominent of these is the Smalltalk programming language developed at Xerox's Palo Alto Research and Development Center (PARC). Everything in Smalltalk is object-oriented. And C++ is a hybrid language. It can be structured programming similar to C, or the new, object-oriented programming. What we say is new is relative. The philosophy of object-oriented programming has been around for over twenty years.

C++ has a very rich library of functions and objects. That is, learning to program in C++ is divided into two parts. The first is to learn C++ itself, and the second is to learn how to use the built-in functions in the C++ standard box.

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